

Small-Scale Domain Switching near Sharp Piezoelectric Bi-material Notches

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Abstract. Assuming small-scale domain switching, the size and shape of the domain switching zone ahead of a sharp generally monoclinic piezoelectric bi-material notch is calculated adopting the energetic switching criterion and micromechanical domain switching model suggested by Hwang et al., (Hwang et al., 1995) for a specified material combination, geometry, and polarization orientation. As the piezoelectric bi-material the combination of piezoelectric ceramics PZT-5H and BaTiO₃ is considered. The asymptotic in-plane field of a bi-material sharp notch is analysed using the expanded Lekhnitskii-Eshelby-Stroh formalism, (Ting, 1996). Next, the boundary value problem with the prescribed spontaneous strain and polarization within the switching domain is solved and their influence on the in-plane intensity of singularity at the tip of interface crack is computed. The effects of the initial poling direction on the resulting variation of the energy release rates are discussed.

INTRODUCTION

Smart structures, such as sensors and actuators, are made of ferroelectric ceramics which are inherently brittle and susceptible to cracking; thus, the important issue of their reliability is raised. These devices usually exhibit a multilayered architecture very often with dissimilar material-bonded joints. Due to a mismatch of material properties across interfaces, a stress singularity at the edge of their interface develops. There is numerous experimental evidence that large singular stresses at vertices of joints may be a cause of fractures and failures in joints. For example, actuators are often found to crack around the edges of internal electrodes. The singularity behaviour of dissimilar piezoelectric material bonded joints was examined in a number of papers, see e.g.(X. L. Xu & Rajapakse, 2000) (Chue & Chen, 2002) (Ou & Wu, 2003)(Chen, 2006) (Ou & Chen, 2004) (Hwu, 2014) (Hirai et al., 2012) (Abe et al., 2017) (Hrstka et al., 2019) (Luangarpa & Koguchi, 2018) and references therein. To understand the singularity behaviour of the bonded joints, two important parameters are needed to explore; (1) the order of stress singularity and (2) the intensity of singularity. The conservative integral based on Betti's reciprocal principle (Sinclair et al., 1984) (Hwu, 2010) (Belov & Kirchner, 1996) (Stern et al., 1976) (Banks-Sills & Sherer, 2002) (Profant et al., 2013) has been proved to be a very efficient too for determining the intensities of singularity at a vertex of the interface in piezoelectric bi-material bonded joints (Hwu, 2014) (Hirai et al., 2012) (Abe et al., 2017) (Hrstka et al., 2019) (Luangarpa & Koguchi, 2018) (Sinclair et al., 1984) (Hwu, 2010) (Belov & Kirchner, 1996). However, this sort of analysis is purely linear and does not consider any nonlinear phenomena dominating

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in the vicinity of the vertex. It is well known that ferroelectric ceramics exhibit strong nonlinear and hysteresis behaviour at a large field strength with domain switching being the source for the hysteresis loop. The domain switching as a possible source of toughening under electrical/mechanical loading in ferroelectrics was analysed by a number of researchers (Park & Sun, 1995) (Hwang et al., 1995) (Zhu & Yang, 1997) (Yang & Zhu, 1998) (Ricoeur & Kuna, 2003) (Z. K. Zhang et al., 2006) (Sheng & Landis, 2007) (Kuna, 2010) (Yang et al., 2001) (Fulton & Gao, 2001a) (Tan et al., 2014) (Fulton & Gao, 2001b) (Rajapakse & Zeng, 2001) (Zeng & Rajapakse, 2001). It was found that domain switching plays an important role in the toughness variation. Due to the concentrated stress and electric fields near the crack tip a domain reorientation takes place. The switched domains induce incompatible strain under the constraint of surrounding un-switched material which leads to the stress redistribution near the crack tip. The apparent toughness of ferroelectrics thus varies due to domain switching. Assuming that these non-elastic processes are restricted to regions around the crack tip, which are small compared to relevant crack lengths, the concepts of linear elastic fracture mechanics can be applied. As a results, several simple domain switching models have been proposed in literature to estimate crack tip process zones in ferroelectrics, which can

Fig. 1 Geometry of a bi-material notch characterized by two regions I and II. Notch faces are defined by angles ω_1 and ω_2 . Material interface is always considered at $\theta = 0$. Angles α_1 and α_2 denote poling direction of the materials I and II, respectively

successfully predict possible toughening or softening effects (Hwang et al., 1995) (Ricoeur & Kuna, 2003) (Rajapakse & Zeng, 2001) (Wang & Zhang, 2007). It should be noted that a large scale domain switching was modelled using the phase field model, which is not restricted to small-scale domain switching and the effects on fracture of ferroelectric materials were analysed in (Schrade et al., 2007) (Wang & Kamlah, 2009) (B. X. Xu et al., 2010) (Sluka et al., 2012) (Abdollahi & Arias, 2012) (Su et al., 2015) (Van Lich et al., 2015) (Yu et al., 2016) (Q. Zhang & Su, 2018). However, it should be noted that all these estimates were performed for crack-like flaws in homogenous materials. There are no attempts to analyse the domain switching and the resulting variation of the intensity of singularity at a vertex of the interface in piezoelectric bi-material bonded joints or at the tip of interface crack. Such a configuration is however typical for sensors and actuators in smart structures and it will be addressed in this paper.

PROBLEM FORMULATION AND SOLUTION METHODS

General geometry of the considered bi-material notch is illustrated in Fig. 1. Each wedge occupies the region $0 < \theta < \omega_1$ or $\omega_2 < \theta < \pi$.

With respect to the material symmetry, the monoclinic materials with the symmetry axis parallel to $x_3 = 0$ are considered. Their elasticity and piezoelectricity matrices have the following structure:

$$\mathbf{C}_E = \begin{bmatrix} C_{11}^E & C_{12}^E & C_{13}^E & 0 & 0 & C_{16}^E \\ C_{12}^E & C_{22}^E & C_{23}^E & 0 & 0 & C_{26}^E \\ C_{13}^E & C_{23}^E & C_{33}^E & 0 & 0 & C_{36}^E \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & C_{44}^E & C_{45}^E & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & C_{45}^E & C_{55}^E & 0 \\ C_{16}^E & C_{26}^E & C_{36}^E & 0 & 0 & C_{66}^E \end{bmatrix}, \quad (1)$$

$$\mathbf{e} = \begin{bmatrix} e_{11} & e_{12} & e_{13} & 0 & 0 & e_{16} \\ e_{21} & e_{22} & e_{23} & 0 & 0 & e_{26} \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & e_{34} & e_{35} & 0 \end{bmatrix}, \quad \boldsymbol{\omega}_\varepsilon = \begin{bmatrix} \omega_{11}^\varepsilon & \omega_{12}^\varepsilon & 0 \\ \omega_{12}^\varepsilon & \omega_{22}^\varepsilon & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & \omega_{33}^\varepsilon \end{bmatrix}, \quad (2)$$

where \mathbf{C}_E is the elastic stiffness tensor at constant electric field, \mathbf{e} is the piezoelectric tensor, and $\boldsymbol{\omega}_\varepsilon$ is the dielectric permittivity tensor at constant strain. The directional properties of the matrices depend on the poling axis, which can attain two limit configurations, either it coincides with x_1 -axis or with x_2 -axis. Between these states their structure corresponds to the above mentioned monoclinic one. External loads are assumed to be parallel to the plane defined by $x_3 = 0$ and plane strain deformations characterized by linear piezoelectricity are considered. These assumptions allow to decouple the in-plane and anti-plane relations and to solve the in-plane and anti-plane problem separately. In the following only the in-plane problem is considered. The constitutive relations can be expressed as

$$\begin{Bmatrix} \boldsymbol{\varepsilon} \\ -\mathbf{E} \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \hat{\mathbf{S}}_D' & \hat{\mathbf{g}}'^T \\ \hat{\mathbf{g}}' & -\hat{\boldsymbol{\beta}}_\sigma' \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} \boldsymbol{\sigma} \\ \mathbf{D} \end{Bmatrix}, \quad (3)$$

where

$$\boldsymbol{\sigma} = \begin{Bmatrix} \sigma_1 \\ \sigma_2 \\ \sigma_6 \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{Bmatrix} \sigma_{11} \\ \sigma_{22} \\ \sigma_{12} \end{Bmatrix}, \quad \boldsymbol{\varepsilon} = \begin{Bmatrix} \varepsilon_1 \\ \varepsilon_2 \\ \varepsilon_6 \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{Bmatrix} \varepsilon_{11} \\ \varepsilon_{22} \\ 2\varepsilon_{12} \end{Bmatrix}, \quad \mathbf{E} = \begin{Bmatrix} E_1 \\ E_2 \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{Bmatrix} -\frac{\partial \phi}{\partial x_1} \\ -\frac{\partial \phi}{\partial x_2} \end{Bmatrix}, \quad \mathbf{D} = \begin{Bmatrix} D_1 \\ D_2 \end{Bmatrix} \quad (4)$$

are the stress vector, the strain vector, the electric field vector, the electric potential, and the electric displacement vector, respectively,

$$\hat{\mathbf{S}}_D' = \begin{bmatrix} \hat{S}_{11}^{D'} & \hat{S}_{12}^{D'} & \hat{S}_{16}^{D'} \\ \hat{S}_{12}^{D'} & \hat{S}_{22}^{D'} & \hat{S}_{26}^{D'} \\ \hat{S}_{16}^{D'} & \hat{S}_{26}^{D'} & \hat{S}_{66}^{D'} \end{bmatrix}, \quad \hat{\mathbf{g}}' = \begin{bmatrix} \hat{g}'_{11} & \hat{g}'_{12} & \hat{g}'_{16} \\ \hat{g}'_{21} & \hat{g}'_{22} & \hat{g}'_{26} \end{bmatrix}, \quad \hat{\boldsymbol{\beta}}_\sigma' = \begin{bmatrix} \hat{\beta}'_{11} & \hat{\beta}'_{12} \\ \hat{\beta}'_{12} & \hat{\beta}'_{22} \end{bmatrix} \quad (5)$$

where $\hat{\mathbf{S}}_D'$, $\hat{\mathbf{g}}'$, $\hat{\boldsymbol{\beta}}_\sigma'$ are the compliance matrix at constant induction, the piezoelectric strain/voltage matrix, and the dielectric impermeability matrix at constant stress, respectively, evaluated under the assumption of the generalized plane strain a short circuit $\varepsilon_3=0$ and $E_3 = 0$ as

$$\hat{S}_{ij}^{D'} = \hat{S}_{ij}^D + \frac{\hat{g}_{3i}\hat{g}_{3j}}{\hat{\beta}_{33}^\sigma} = \hat{S}_{ji}^{D'}, \quad \hat{g}'_{ij} = \hat{g}_{ij} - \frac{\hat{\beta}_{3i}^\sigma \hat{g}_{3j}}{\hat{\beta}_{33}^\sigma}, \quad \hat{\beta}'_{ij} = \hat{\beta}_{ij}^\sigma - \frac{\hat{\beta}_{3i}^\sigma \hat{\beta}_{3j}^\sigma}{\hat{\beta}_{33}^\sigma} = \hat{\beta}_{ji}^{\prime\sigma}, \quad (6)$$

$$\hat{S}_{ij}^D = S_{ij}^D \frac{S_{3i}^D S_{3j}^D}{S_{33}^D} = \hat{S}_{ji}^D, \quad \hat{g}_{ij} = g_{ij} \frac{g_{i3} S_{3j}^D}{S_{33}^D}, \quad \hat{\beta}_{ij}^\sigma = \beta_{ij}^\sigma \frac{g_{i3} g_{j3}}{S_{33}^D} = \hat{\beta}_{ji}^\sigma \quad (7)$$

for $i, j \neq 3$, where

$$\mathbf{S}_D = \mathbf{C}_E^{-1} - \mathbf{C}_E^{-1} \mathbf{e}^T \boldsymbol{\omega}_\sigma^{-1} \mathbf{e} \mathbf{C}_E^{-1}, \quad \boldsymbol{\omega}_\sigma = \mathbf{e} \mathbf{C}_E^{-1} \mathbf{e}^T + \boldsymbol{\omega}_\varepsilon, \quad \mathbf{g} = \boldsymbol{\omega}_\sigma^{-1} \mathbf{e} \mathbf{C}_E^{-1}.$$

The inverse form of the constitutive relations in Eq. (3) reads

$$\begin{Bmatrix} \boldsymbol{\sigma} \\ \mathbf{D} \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \hat{\mathbf{C}}_E' & \hat{\mathbf{e}}'^T \\ \hat{\mathbf{e}}' & -\hat{\boldsymbol{\omega}}_\varepsilon' \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} \boldsymbol{\varepsilon} \\ -\mathbf{E} \end{Bmatrix}, \quad (8)$$

where the in-plane elasticity and piezoelectricity matrices under the assumption of the generalized plane strain and short circuit have the following structure:

$$\hat{\mathbf{C}}_E' = \begin{bmatrix} \hat{C}_{11}'^E & \hat{C}_{12}'^E & \hat{C}_{16}'^E \\ \hat{C}_{12}'^E & \hat{C}_{22}'^E & \hat{C}_{26}'^E \\ \hat{C}_{16}'^E & \hat{C}_{26}'^E & \hat{C}_{66}'^E \end{bmatrix}, \quad \hat{\mathbf{e}}' = \begin{bmatrix} \hat{e}_{11}' & \hat{e}_{12}' & \hat{e}_{16}' \\ \hat{e}_{21}' & \hat{e}_{22}' & \hat{e}_{26}' \end{bmatrix}, \quad \hat{\boldsymbol{\omega}}_\varepsilon' = \begin{bmatrix} \hat{\omega}_{11}'^\varepsilon & \hat{\omega}_{12}'^\varepsilon \\ \hat{\omega}_{21}'^\varepsilon & \hat{\omega}_{22}'^\varepsilon \end{bmatrix} \quad (9)$$

with

$$\begin{aligned} e'_{ij} &= e_{ij} - \frac{\omega_{3i}^\varepsilon e_{3j}}{\omega_{33}^\varepsilon}, \quad \hat{e}_{ij} = e_{ij} - \frac{e_{3i} C_{3j}^E}{C_{33}^E}, \quad \hat{e}'_{ij} = \hat{e}_{ij} - \frac{\hat{\omega}_{3i}^\varepsilon \hat{e}_{3j}}{\hat{\omega}_{33}^\varepsilon}, \\ \omega'_{ij} &= \omega_{ij} - \frac{\omega_{3i}^\varepsilon \omega_{3j}^\varepsilon}{\omega_{33}^\varepsilon}, \quad \hat{\omega}'_{ij} = \omega_{ij} + \frac{e_{3i} e_{3j}}{C_{33}^E}, \quad \hat{\omega}'_{ij} = \hat{\omega}_{ij} - \frac{\hat{\omega}_{3i}^\varepsilon \hat{\omega}_{3j}^\varepsilon}{\hat{\omega}_{33}^\varepsilon} = \hat{\omega}'_{ji} \\ \hat{C}'_{ij} &= C_{ij}^E = C_{ij}^E, \quad \hat{e}'_{ij} = e'_{ij} = e_{ij}. \end{aligned} \quad (10)$$

Characteristic matrices of the material are non-degenerate when the poling direction is perpendicular to the x_3 axis and semi-degenerate or degenerate otherwise. Only non-degenerate cases are considered thereafter.

Note that the in-plane problem of the stress singularity at the sharp notch composed of the two monoclinic piezoelectric materials is characterized by two generally complex exponents $\delta_1 - 1$, $\delta_2 - 1$ and one real exponent $\delta_3 - 1$. The resulting displacements and stresses are obtained as the superposition of these particular singular contributions weighted by the generally complex amplitudes. The amplitudes are introduced in the similar manner as for a crack and referred to as the generalized stress intensity factors (GSIFs). The following vectors are introduced

$$\mathbf{u} = \begin{Bmatrix} u_1 \\ u_2 \\ \phi \end{Bmatrix}, \quad \mathbf{T} = \begin{Bmatrix} T_1 \\ T_2 \\ T_D \end{Bmatrix}, \quad (11)$$

where u_1, u_2 are the displacement components, ϕ is the electric potential, T_1, T_2 and T_D are the components of the resulting tractions and the electric charge q along the semi-infinite line passing through the origin of the coordinate system $x_1 x_2$. The coupled electromechanical field near the notch vertex can be approximated as

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{u}(r, \theta) &= H_1 r^{\delta_1} \boldsymbol{\eta}_1(\theta) + H_2 r^{\delta_2} \boldsymbol{\eta}_2(\theta) + H_3 r^{\delta_3} \boldsymbol{\eta}_3(\theta), \\ \mathbf{T}(r, \theta) &= H_1 r^{\delta_1} \boldsymbol{\lambda}_1(\theta) + H_2 r^{\delta_2} \boldsymbol{\lambda}_2(\theta) + H_3 r^{\delta_3} \boldsymbol{\lambda}_3(\theta), \end{aligned} \quad (12)$$

where H_i are generalized stress intensity factors, r and θ are polar coordinates, see Fig. 1, and

$$\boldsymbol{\eta}_i(\theta) = \mathbf{A} \mathbf{Z}^{\delta_i}(\theta) \mathbf{v}_i + \overline{\mathbf{A}} \mathbf{Z}^{\delta_i}(\theta) \mathbf{w}_i, \quad (13)$$

$$\lambda_i(\theta) = \mathbf{L}\mathbf{Z}^{\delta_i}(\theta)\mathbf{v}_i + \overline{\mathbf{L}\mathbf{Z}^{\delta_i}(\theta)}\mathbf{w}_i.$$

where the complex function \mathbf{Z}^{δ_i} and matrices \mathbf{A} and \mathbf{L} are defined in Appendix A, the bar above the symbols denotes complex conjugate quantities. \mathbf{v}_i and \mathbf{w}_i are eigenvectors pertinent to the singularity exponent eigenvalue problem of the considered sharp notch in Fig. 1. Considering traction and charge free notch faces the following boundary conditions are imposed:

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{T}^I(\omega_1) &= 0, \\ \mathbf{T}^{II}(\omega_2) &= 0. \end{aligned} \quad (14)$$

The displacement and traction continuity conditions are prescribed along the interface $\theta = 0$ as

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{u}^I(0) &= \mathbf{u}^{II}(0), \\ \mathbf{T}^I(0) &= \mathbf{T}^{II}(0). \end{aligned} \quad (15)$$

By substituting vector functions $\lambda_i(\theta)$ and $\eta_i(\theta)$ from Eq. (13) into Eqs. (14) and (15), one gets the singularity exponent eigenvalue problem formed by twelve homogeneous algebraic equations, which can be written in the matrix form as

$$\begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{X}_1^I & \overline{\mathbf{X}}_1^I & \mathbf{0} & \mathbf{0} \\ \mathbf{0} & \mathbf{0} & \mathbf{X}_2^{II} & \overline{\mathbf{X}}_2^{II} \\ \mathbf{B}_0^I & \overline{\mathbf{B}}_0^I & -\mathbf{B}_0^{II} & \overline{\mathbf{B}}_0^{II} \\ \mathbf{I} & \mathbf{I} & -\mathbf{I} & -\mathbf{I} \end{bmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} \mathbf{L}^I \mathbf{v}^I \\ \overline{\mathbf{L}}^I \mathbf{w}^I \\ \mathbf{L}^{II} \mathbf{v}^{II} \\ \overline{\mathbf{L}}^{II} \mathbf{w}^{II} \end{pmatrix} = \mathbf{0}, \quad (16)$$

where

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{X}_j &= \mathbf{L}\mathbf{Z}_j^{\delta}(\omega_j)(\mathbf{L})^{-1}, \quad \overline{\mathbf{X}}_j = \overline{\mathbf{L}\mathbf{Z}_j^{\delta}(\omega_j)(\mathbf{L})^{-1}}, \quad (j = 1,2) \\ \mathbf{B}_0 &= i\mathbf{A}\mathbf{L}^{-1}, \quad \overline{\mathbf{B}}_0 = -i\overline{\mathbf{A}\mathbf{L}^{-1}}. \end{aligned} \quad (17)$$

and $\mathbf{0}$ denotes 3 x 3 zero matrix on the left-hand side and 12 x 1 zero vector on the right-hand side of Eq. (16). After some algebraic manipulations one receives the characteristic equation for the singularity exponent values in the form

$$\det[\mathbf{K}(\delta)] = 0, \quad (18)$$

where

$$\mathbf{K} = \mathbf{B}_0^I + \overline{\mathbf{B}}_0^I \mathbf{Y}_1^I - (\mathbf{B}_0^{II} + \overline{\mathbf{B}}_0^{II} \mathbf{Y}_2^{II})(\mathbf{I} - \mathbf{Y}_2^{II})^{-1}(\mathbf{I} - \mathbf{Y}_1^I) \quad (19)$$

and

$$\mathbf{Y}_j = \overline{\mathbf{X}}_j^{-1} \mathbf{X}_j, \quad (j = 1,2).$$

For details see (Hrstka et al., 2019).

Let us introduce the following functions:

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{d\tilde{\lambda}_i(\theta)}{dx_1} &= \mathbf{L}\delta_i \mathbf{Z}^{\delta_i-1}(\theta)\mathbf{v}_i + \overline{\mathbf{L}\delta_i \mathbf{Z}^{\delta_i-1}(\theta)}\mathbf{w}_i, \quad i = 1,2,3 \\ \frac{d\tilde{\lambda}_i(\theta)}{dx_2} &= \mathbf{L}\delta_i \mathbf{Z}^{\delta_i-1}(\theta)\boldsymbol{\mu}\mathbf{v}_i + \overline{\mathbf{L}\delta_i \mathbf{Z}^{\delta_i-1}(\theta)}\overline{\boldsymbol{\mu}}\mathbf{w}_i, \quad i = 1,2,3. \end{aligned} \quad (20)$$

Using Eq. (20), the asymptotic stresses and electrical displacements can be written as

$$\sigma^1(r,\theta) = -H_1 r^{\delta_1-1} \frac{d\tilde{\lambda}_1(\theta)}{dx_2} - H_2 r^{\delta_2-1} \frac{d\tilde{\lambda}_2(\theta)}{dx_2} - H_3 r^{\delta_3-1} \frac{d\tilde{\lambda}_3(\theta)}{dx_2}, \sigma^2(r,\theta) = H_1 r^{\delta_1-1} \frac{d\tilde{\lambda}_1(\theta)}{dx_1} + H_2 r^{\delta_2-1} \frac{d\tilde{\lambda}_2(\theta)}{dx_1} + H_3 r^{\delta_3-1} \frac{d\tilde{\lambda}_3(\theta)}{dx_1}, \quad (21)$$

where

$$\sigma^1 = \begin{Bmatrix} \sigma_{11} \\ \sigma_{12} \\ D_1 \end{Bmatrix}, \sigma^2 = \begin{Bmatrix} \sigma_{21} \\ \sigma_{22} \\ D_2 \end{Bmatrix},$$

$$\mu = \begin{bmatrix} \mu_1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & \mu_2 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & \mu_3 \end{bmatrix}, \bar{\mu} = \begin{bmatrix} \bar{\mu}_1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & \bar{\mu}_2 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & \bar{\mu}_3 \end{bmatrix}.$$

To determine generalized stress intensity factors in Eq. (12), a conservative line integral for the bi-material notch developed from Betti's reciprocal principle mentioned in the Introduction is applied. Contrary to the J -integral, the path-independence of the line integral developed from Betti's reciprocal principle is also preserved for multi-material stress concentrators if the body forces and charges are neglected. This line integral referred to as the H -integral can be written for a bimaterial notch characterized by angles ω_1 and ω_2 , see Fig. 1, as

$$H(\mathbf{u}, \hat{\mathbf{u}}_i) = \int_{\omega_2}^{\omega_1} (\mathbf{u}^T \hat{\mathbf{t}}_i - \hat{\mathbf{u}}_i^T \mathbf{t}) r d\theta. \quad (22)$$

The vectors $\hat{\mathbf{u}}_i^T$ and $\hat{\mathbf{t}}_i$ are the auxiliary solutions to the displacements, tractions, electric potential and the charge and correspond to the exponent $\hat{\delta}_i = -\delta_i$. The auxiliary solutions are defined as

$$\hat{\mathbf{u}}_i(r,\theta) = r^{-\delta_i} \hat{\boldsymbol{\eta}}_i(\theta),$$

$$\hat{\mathbf{t}}_i(r,\theta) = -\frac{1}{r} \frac{\partial \hat{T}_i(r,\theta)}{\partial \theta} = -r^{-\delta_i-1} \hat{\boldsymbol{\lambda}}_i'(\theta), \quad (i = 1,2,3) \quad (23)$$

where

$$\hat{\boldsymbol{\eta}}_i(\theta) = \mathbf{A} \mathbf{Z}^{-\delta_i}(\theta) \hat{\mathbf{v}}_i + \overline{\mathbf{A} \mathbf{Z}^{-\delta_i}(\theta)} \hat{\mathbf{w}}_i,$$

$$\hat{\boldsymbol{\lambda}}_i'(\theta) = \mathbf{L}(\mathbf{Z}^{-\delta_i}(\theta))' \hat{\mathbf{v}}_i + \overline{\mathbf{L}(\mathbf{Z}^{-\delta_i}(\theta))}' \hat{\mathbf{w}}_i,$$

where $(\cdot)'$ denotes the differentiation with respect to θ . Observe that the vectors \mathbf{u} and \mathbf{t} in Eq.(22) represent either the regular asymptotic or a full field solution obtained numerically e.g. by FEM. In the first case, the vector \mathbf{u} is given by Eq.(12)₁ and the vector \mathbf{t} is given by the derivative of Eq.(12)₂ with respect to θ similarly as $\hat{\mathbf{t}}_i$ in Eq. (23)₂. The full-field solution reduces to the asymptotic solution if the integration contour shrinks to the notch tip. Since the regular and corresponding auxiliary solutions are orthogonal with respect to the "scalar product" defined by the integral (22), i.e.

$$H(r^{\delta_i} \boldsymbol{\eta}_j(\theta), r^{-\delta_i} \hat{\boldsymbol{\eta}}_i(\theta)) = \begin{cases} \text{const} \neq 0 & \text{for } i = j, \\ 0 & \text{for } i \neq j, \end{cases} \quad (24)$$

an important result for the GSIFs evaluation follows as

$$H_i = \frac{H(\mathbf{u}^{FEM}, r_c^{-\delta_i} \hat{\boldsymbol{\eta}}_i(\theta))}{H(r_c^{\delta_i} \hat{\boldsymbol{\eta}}_i(\theta), r_c^{-\delta_i} \hat{\boldsymbol{\eta}}_i(\theta))} \quad (i = 1, 2, 3), \quad (25)$$

where

$$\begin{aligned} & H(\mathbf{u}^{FEM}, r_c^{-\delta_i} \hat{\boldsymbol{\eta}}_i(\theta)) = \\ & = \int_{\omega_2}^{\omega_1} \left((\mathbf{u}^{FEM})^T r_c^{-\delta_i-1} \hat{\boldsymbol{\lambda}}_i'(\theta) + r_c^{-\delta_i} \hat{\boldsymbol{\eta}}_i^T(\theta) \mathbf{t}^{FEM} \right) r_c d\theta \end{aligned} \quad (26)$$

with \mathbf{u}^{FEM} and \mathbf{t}^{FEM} standing for the FEM approximation to the vectors \mathbf{u} and \mathbf{t} , respectively, and with r_c denoting the radius of the circular path remote from the notch singularity. Elements of vector \mathbf{t}^{FEM} along the integrating contour have to be computed from the stresses using the Cauchy formula $t_i = \sigma_{ij} n_j$, in the matrix form written as $\mathbf{t}^{FEM} = \boldsymbol{\sigma}^{FEM} \mathbf{n}$, where $\boldsymbol{\sigma}^{FEM}$ is the two-dimensional generalized stress tensor and \mathbf{n} is the outer normal to the domain enclosed by the circular integrating path of the radius r_c defined as

$$\boldsymbol{\sigma}^{FEM} = \begin{bmatrix} \sigma_{11}^{FEM} & \sigma_{12}^{FEM} \\ \sigma_{21}^{FEM} & \sigma_{22}^{FEM} \\ D_1^{FEM} & D_2^{FEM} \end{bmatrix}, \quad \mathbf{n} = \begin{Bmatrix} \cos(\theta) \\ \sin(\theta) \end{Bmatrix}. \quad (27)$$

For to predict the domain switching zone, the energy-based criterion proposed in (Hwang et al., 1995) is applied

$$\sigma_{ij} \Delta \varepsilon_{ij} + E_i \Delta P_i \geq 2P_s E_c, \quad (28)$$

where $\Delta \varepsilon_{ij}$ and ΔP_i are the changes in the spontaneous strain and the spontaneous polarization during switching, respectively. P_s is the magnitude of the spontaneous polarization; and E_c the coercive electric field. As a first approximation it is assumed that stresses σ_{ij} and electrical fields E_i remain unchanged during switching. That means that the linear asymptotic field in Eq. (12) dominates at the notch tip and the loading is thus controlled by the GSIFs H_i . This case is referred to as small scale switching when the size of the switching zone is much smaller than other specimen dimensions. Note that the left-hand side of Eq. (28) represents the specific work dissipated during switching. The threshold value on the right-hand side of Eq. (28) represents approximately half of the area of a polarization hysteresis. Due to electric and/or stress loading the spontaneous polarization of a domain near the notch tip can rotate by 180° , $+90^\circ$ or -90° . Considering that a ferroelectric domain forms an angle α with x_1 axis the changes in spontaneous strain $\Delta \varepsilon_{ij}$ and polarization ΔP_i for 90° domain switchings can be expressed in matrix form as:

$$\Delta \boldsymbol{\varepsilon} = \begin{Bmatrix} \Delta \varepsilon_1 \\ \Delta \varepsilon_2 \\ \Delta \varepsilon_6 \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{Bmatrix} \Delta \varepsilon_{11} \\ \Delta \varepsilon_{22} \\ 2\Delta \varepsilon_{12} \end{Bmatrix} = \gamma_s \begin{Bmatrix} -\cos 2\alpha \\ \cos 2\alpha \\ -2\sin 2\alpha \end{Bmatrix}, \quad (29)$$

$$\Delta \mathbf{P} = \sqrt{2} P_s \begin{bmatrix} \cos\left(\alpha \pm \frac{3\pi}{4}\right) \\ \sin\left(\alpha \pm \frac{3\pi}{4}\right) \end{bmatrix}, \quad (30)$$

where γ_s denotes the spontaneous strain associated with 90° domain switching and $-\frac{3\pi}{4}$ and $\frac{3\pi}{4}$ in Eq. (30) correspond to clockwise and counter clockwise 90° switching, respectively. Note that for 180° $\Delta \varepsilon_{ij} = 0$ and $\Delta \mathbf{P} = -2P_s [\cos \alpha \quad \sin \alpha]^T$. A variation of the local stress/electric fields near the vertex induced by domain switching leads to the additional GSIFs ΔH_i which are evaluated again using Betti's reciprocal principle.

To start with, consider *initial* generalized stress tensor $\{\boldsymbol{\sigma}_r(\mathbf{u}_r), \mathbf{D}_r(\mathbf{u}_r)\}^T$, and *initial* generalized strain tensor $\{\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_r(\mathbf{u}_r), -\mathbf{E}_r(\mathbf{u}_r)\}^T$ in the body. Generalized stress $\{\boldsymbol{\sigma}_r(\mathbf{u}_r), \mathbf{D}_r(\mathbf{u}_r)\}^T$ developed due to changes in spontaneous strain $\Delta\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}$ and polarization $\Delta\mathbf{P}$ satisfies equilibrium

$$\partial \begin{Bmatrix} \boldsymbol{\sigma}_r \\ \mathbf{D}_r \end{Bmatrix} = 0 \text{ in } \Omega, \quad (31)$$

where the matrix differential operator is defined as

$$\partial = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{\partial}{\partial x_1} & 0 & \frac{\partial}{\partial x_2} & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & \frac{\partial}{\partial x_2} & \frac{\partial}{\partial x_1} & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & \frac{\partial}{\partial x_1} & \frac{\partial}{\partial x_2} \end{bmatrix},$$

and Ω denotes the whole bimaterial body with the body forces and free charges absent. Further, $\{\boldsymbol{\sigma}_r(\mathbf{u}_r), \mathbf{D}_r(\mathbf{u}_r)\}^T$ satisfies the constitutive law in Ω

$$\begin{Bmatrix} \boldsymbol{\sigma}_r \\ \mathbf{D}_r - \Delta\mathbf{P} \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \hat{\mathbf{C}}'_E & \hat{\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}}'^T \\ \hat{\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}}' & -\hat{\boldsymbol{\omega}}'_\varepsilon \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_r - \Delta\boldsymbol{\varepsilon} \\ -\mathbf{E}_r \end{Bmatrix}, \quad (32)$$

or rewritten as

$$\begin{Bmatrix} \boldsymbol{\sigma}_r \\ \mathbf{D}_r \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \hat{\mathbf{C}}'_E & \hat{\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}}'^T \\ \hat{\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}}' & -\hat{\boldsymbol{\omega}}'_\varepsilon \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_r \\ -\mathbf{E}_r \end{Bmatrix} - \begin{Bmatrix} \hat{\mathbf{C}}'_E \Delta\boldsymbol{\varepsilon} \\ \hat{\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}}' \Delta\boldsymbol{\varepsilon} - \Delta\mathbf{P} \end{Bmatrix}, \quad (33)$$

with $\hat{\mathbf{C}}'_E, \hat{\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}}', \hat{\boldsymbol{\omega}}'_\varepsilon$ having the same structure as given in Eq. (9) and $\Delta\boldsymbol{\varepsilon} = \Delta\mathbf{P} = 0$ outside the switching zone Ω_{SZ} . The boundary and continuity conditions are as follows:

$$\mathbf{t}_r = [\mathbf{n}] \begin{Bmatrix} \boldsymbol{\sigma}_r \\ \mathbf{D}_r \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} n_1 & 0 & n_2 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & n_2 & n_1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & n_1 & n_2 \end{bmatrix} \cdot \begin{Bmatrix} \boldsymbol{\sigma}_r \\ \mathbf{D}_r \end{Bmatrix} = 0, \text{ on } \partial\Omega \quad (34)$$

where n_1, n_2 are components of the unit outer normal vector. Across the boundary of the switching zone $\partial\Omega_{SZ}$ the tractions and the displacements are continuous

$$\llbracket \mathbf{t}_r \rrbracket = \llbracket [\mathbf{n}] \begin{Bmatrix} \boldsymbol{\sigma}_r \\ \mathbf{D}_r - \Delta\mathbf{P} \end{Bmatrix} \rrbracket = 0, \llbracket \mathbf{u}_r \rrbracket = \llbracket \begin{Bmatrix} u_{1r} \\ u_{2r} \\ \phi_r \end{Bmatrix} \rrbracket = 0 \text{ on } \partial\Omega_{SZ}, \quad (35)$$

where the double brackets $\llbracket \cdot \rrbracket$ denote a jump of the quantity inside. Finally, the tractions and displacements are required to be continuous along the interface

$$\mathbf{u}_r^I = \begin{Bmatrix} u_{1r}^I \\ u_{2r}^I \\ \phi_r^I \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{Bmatrix} u_{1r}^{II} \\ u_{2r}^{II} \\ \phi_r^{II} \end{Bmatrix} = \mathbf{u}_r^{II}, \mathbf{t}_r^I = \mathbf{t}_r^{II}. \quad (36)$$

The generalized strain tensor $\{\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_r(\mathbf{u}_r), -\mathbf{E}_r(\mathbf{u}_r)\}^T$ satisfies

$$\begin{Bmatrix} \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_r \\ -\mathbf{E}_r \end{Bmatrix} = \partial^T \mathbf{u}_r. \quad (37)$$

For arbitrary virtual displacement $\delta \mathbf{u}$ the weak form of the problem given by the equations (31) -(36) reads

$$\begin{aligned} \int_{\Omega} (\hat{\mathbf{C}}'_E \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_r - \hat{\mathbf{e}}'^T \mathbf{E}_r) \delta \boldsymbol{\varepsilon} d\Omega + \int_{\Omega} (\hat{\mathbf{e}}' \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_r + \hat{\boldsymbol{\omega}}'_\varepsilon \mathbf{E}_r) \delta \mathbf{E} d\Omega = \\ = \int_{\Omega_{SZ}} [\hat{\mathbf{C}}'_E \Delta \boldsymbol{\varepsilon} \delta \boldsymbol{\varepsilon} + (\hat{\mathbf{e}}' \Delta \boldsymbol{\varepsilon} + \Delta \mathbf{P}) \delta \mathbf{E}] d\Omega. \end{aligned} \quad (38)$$

Eq. (38) forms a basis of mixed finite element formulation.

Considering the initial generalized stress and strain tensor, the reciprocal theorem for two arbitrary admissible fields \mathbf{u} and $\hat{\mathbf{u}}$ (the auxiliary field in our case) reads

$$\int_{D=D'+D''} \left[\{\boldsymbol{\sigma}(\mathbf{u}), \mathbf{D}(\mathbf{u})\} - \{\boldsymbol{\sigma}_r(\mathbf{u}_r), \mathbf{D}_r(\mathbf{u}_r)\} \right] \begin{Bmatrix} \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}(\hat{\mathbf{u}}) \\ -\mathbf{E}(\hat{\mathbf{u}}) \end{Bmatrix} - \{\boldsymbol{\sigma}(\hat{\mathbf{u}}), \mathbf{D}(\hat{\mathbf{u}})\} \begin{Bmatrix} \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}(\mathbf{u}) \\ -\mathbf{E}(\mathbf{u}) \end{Bmatrix} - \begin{Bmatrix} \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_r(\mathbf{u}_r) \\ -\mathbf{E}_r(\mathbf{u}_r) \end{Bmatrix} \quad (39)$$

or

$$\int_{D=D'+D''} \left[\{\boldsymbol{\sigma}(\mathbf{u}), \mathbf{D}(\mathbf{u})\} \partial^T \hat{\mathbf{u}} - \{\boldsymbol{\sigma}(\hat{\mathbf{u}}), \mathbf{D}(\hat{\mathbf{u}})\} \partial^T \mathbf{u} - \{\boldsymbol{\sigma}_r(\mathbf{u}_r), \mathbf{D}_r(\mathbf{u}_r)\} \begin{Bmatrix} \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}(\hat{\mathbf{u}}) \\ -\mathbf{E}(\hat{\mathbf{u}}) \end{Bmatrix} + \{\boldsymbol{\sigma}(\hat{\mathbf{u}}), \mathbf{D}(\hat{\mathbf{u}})\} \begin{Bmatrix} \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}(\mathbf{u}) \\ -\mathbf{E}(\mathbf{u}) \end{Bmatrix} \right] \quad (40)$$

where the domain D is any subset of the original domain obtained by excluding the crack tip. The boundary of D is made up of arbitrary contours C_1 and C_2 circumventing the crack tip and connecting the traction free crack faces. C_2 is a remote path whereas C_1 is a path very close to the crack tip. Clearly, the integration over the subdomains D' and D'' is performed using pertinent generalized stress and strain fields in the respective subdomains. Observe that it holds

$$\{\boldsymbol{\sigma}(\hat{\mathbf{u}}), \mathbf{D}(\hat{\mathbf{u}})\} = \begin{Bmatrix} \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}(\hat{\mathbf{u}}) \\ -\mathbf{E}(\hat{\mathbf{u}}) \end{Bmatrix}^T \begin{bmatrix} \hat{\mathbf{C}}'_E & \hat{\mathbf{e}}'^T \\ \hat{\mathbf{e}}' & -\hat{\boldsymbol{\omega}}'_\varepsilon \end{bmatrix} \quad (41)$$

and the last term in Eq. (40) can be written using Eq. (33) as

$$\begin{aligned} \{\boldsymbol{\sigma}(\hat{\mathbf{u}}), \mathbf{D}(\hat{\mathbf{u}})\} \begin{Bmatrix} \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_r(\mathbf{u}_r) \\ -\mathbf{E}_r(\mathbf{u}_r) \end{Bmatrix} = \{\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_r(\mathbf{u}_r), -\mathbf{E}_r(\mathbf{u}_r)\} \begin{bmatrix} \hat{\mathbf{C}}'_E & \hat{\mathbf{e}}'^T \\ \hat{\mathbf{e}}' & -\hat{\boldsymbol{\omega}}'_\varepsilon \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}(\hat{\mathbf{u}}) \\ -\mathbf{E}(\hat{\mathbf{u}}) \end{Bmatrix} = \{\boldsymbol{\sigma}_r(\mathbf{u}_r), \mathbf{D}_r(\mathbf{u}_r)\} \begin{Bmatrix} \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}(\hat{\mathbf{u}}) \\ -\mathbf{E}(\hat{\mathbf{u}}) \end{Bmatrix} \\ + \{\hat{\mathbf{C}}'_E \Delta \boldsymbol{\varepsilon} \quad \hat{\mathbf{e}}' \Delta \boldsymbol{\varepsilon} - \Delta \mathbf{P}\} \begin{Bmatrix} \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}(\hat{\mathbf{u}}) \\ -\mathbf{E}(\hat{\mathbf{u}}) \end{Bmatrix}. \end{aligned} \quad (42)$$

Applying the divergence theorem to the first two terms in Eq. (40) one obtains

$$\int_{C=C_1 \cup C_2} [\{\boldsymbol{\sigma}(\mathbf{u}), \mathbf{D}(\mathbf{u})\} [\mathbf{n}]^T \hat{\mathbf{u}} - \{\boldsymbol{\sigma}(\hat{\mathbf{u}}), \mathbf{D}(\hat{\mathbf{u}})\} [\mathbf{n}]^T \mathbf{u}] ds = - \int_{D=D'+D''} \{\hat{\mathbf{C}}'_E \Delta \boldsymbol{\varepsilon} \quad \hat{\mathbf{e}}' \Delta \boldsymbol{\varepsilon} - \Delta \mathbf{P}\} \begin{Bmatrix} \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}(\hat{\mathbf{u}}) \\ -\mathbf{E}(\hat{\mathbf{u}}) \end{Bmatrix} \quad (43)$$

Reversing the flow direction of the contour C_1 and using FE approximation to the field \mathbf{u} along the contour C_2 we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} & \int_{C_1} [\{\boldsymbol{\sigma}(\mathbf{u}), \mathbf{D}(\mathbf{u})\}[\mathbf{n}]^T \hat{\mathbf{u}} - \{\boldsymbol{\sigma}(\hat{\mathbf{u}}), \mathbf{D}(\hat{\mathbf{u}})\}[\mathbf{n}]^T \mathbf{u}] ds \\ &= \int_{C_2} [\{\boldsymbol{\sigma}(\mathbf{u}), \mathbf{D}(\mathbf{u})\}^{FEM}[\mathbf{n}]^T \hat{\mathbf{u}} - \{\boldsymbol{\sigma}(\hat{\mathbf{u}}), \mathbf{D}(\hat{\mathbf{u}})\}[\mathbf{n}]^T \mathbf{u}^{FEM}] ds + \int_{D=D'+D''} \left\{ \hat{\mathbf{C}}_E' \Delta \boldsymbol{\varepsilon} \quad \hat{\mathbf{e}}' \right. \\ & \left. \right\} \left\{ \begin{array}{l} \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}(\hat{\mathbf{u}}) \\ -\mathbf{E}(\hat{\mathbf{u}}) \end{array} \right\} dS. \end{aligned} \quad (44)$$

To determine the local GSIFs H_i^{tip} , Eq. (44) is rewritten using the approach described above in Eqs. (22) – (26) and H_i^{tip} are calculated as

$$H_i^{tip} = \frac{H(\mathbf{u}^{FEM}, r_c^{-\delta_i} \hat{\boldsymbol{\eta}}_i(\theta)) - \int_{D=D'+D''} \left\{ \hat{\mathbf{C}}_E' \Delta \boldsymbol{\varepsilon} \quad \hat{\mathbf{e}}' \Delta \boldsymbol{\varepsilon} - \Delta \mathbf{P} \right\} \left\{ \begin{array}{l} \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}(r^{-\delta_i} \hat{\boldsymbol{\eta}}_i(\theta)) \\ -\mathbf{E}(r^{-\delta_i} \hat{\boldsymbol{\eta}}_i(\theta)) \end{array} \right\} dS}{H(r^{\delta_i} \boldsymbol{\eta}_i(\theta), r^{-\delta_i} \hat{\boldsymbol{\eta}}_i(\theta))}, \quad i = 1, 2, 3 \quad (45)$$

The additional GSIFs ΔH_i , $i = 1, 2, 3$ due to the shielding or antishielding effects of the switching zone are then given by

$$H_i^{tip} = H_i + \Delta H_i \quad (i = 1, 2, 3). \quad (46)$$

where H_i are calculated from Eq. (25).

GSIFs H_i and or $H_i + \Delta H_i$ are not much convenient for a formulation of fracture mechanics criteria for two reasons: (1) they have an awkward physical unit due to imaginary part of the singularity exponent, (2) H_i contain a mixture of mechanical and electrical loading. The first problem can be removed according to the Rice concept (Rice, 1988) by introducing a reference length l which may be chosen arbitrarily and defining modified GSIFs as follows

$$\tilde{H}_i = H_i l^{i \operatorname{Im}(\delta_i)} \quad (i = 1, 2, 3), \quad (47)$$

where $\operatorname{Im}(\delta_i)$ stands for the imaginary part of δ_i . Then along $\theta = 0$ ahead of the notch tip the asymptotic stresses and electrical displacements can be expressed in matrix form using Eq. (21)₂ as

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} \sigma_{21} \\ \sigma_{22} \\ D_2 \end{array} \right\}_{\theta=0} = \underbrace{\left[\frac{d\tilde{\lambda}_1(0)}{dx_1} \quad \frac{d\tilde{\lambda}_2(0)}{dx_1} \quad \frac{d\tilde{\lambda}_3(0)}{dx_1} \right]}_{A_{x_1}} \langle r^{\operatorname{Re}(\delta_i)-1} \rangle \left\langle \left(\frac{r}{l} \right)^{i \operatorname{Im}(\delta_i)} \right\rangle \left\{ \begin{array}{l} \tilde{H}_1 \\ \tilde{H}_2 \\ \tilde{H}_3 \end{array} \right\}. \quad (48)$$

The brackets $\langle \cdot \rangle$ denote the 3x3 diagonal matrix

$$\langle r^{\operatorname{Re}(\delta_i)-1} \rangle = \begin{bmatrix} r^{\operatorname{Re}(\delta_1)-1} & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & r^{\operatorname{Re}(\delta_2)-1} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & r^{\operatorname{Re}(\delta_3)-1} \end{bmatrix}, \quad \left\langle \left(\frac{r}{l} \right)^{i \operatorname{Im}(\delta_i)} \right\rangle = \begin{bmatrix} \left(\frac{r}{l} \right)^{i \operatorname{Im}(\delta_1)} & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & \left(\frac{r}{l} \right)^{i \operatorname{Im}(\delta_2)} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & \left(\frac{r}{l} \right)^{i \operatorname{Im}(\delta_3)} \end{bmatrix}.$$

The modified GSIFs follow from Eq.(48) as

$$\begin{Bmatrix} \tilde{H}_1 \\ \tilde{H}_2 \\ \tilde{H}_3 \end{Bmatrix} = \lim_{r \rightarrow 0} \langle r^{1-\text{Re}(\delta_i)} \rangle \left\langle \left(\frac{r}{l}\right)^{-i\text{Im}(\delta_i)} \right\rangle \tilde{\Lambda}_{,x_1}^{-1} \begin{Bmatrix} \sigma_{21} \\ \sigma_{22} \\ D_2 \end{Bmatrix}_{\theta=0}. \quad (49)$$

However, as stated by Hwu and Ikeda (Hwu & Ikeda, 2008), the GSIFs still cannot be reduced to classical stress intensity factors for a notch tip in a homogeneous medium, because the directions of $\frac{d\tilde{\lambda}_1(0)}{dx_1}, \frac{d\tilde{\lambda}_2(0)}{dx_1}, \frac{d\tilde{\lambda}_3(0)}{dx_1}$ are usually not the same as the direction of the crack. They suggested a transformation consisting in the pre-multiplication by the matrix $\tilde{\Lambda}_{,x_1}$, see Eq.(48), to obtain classical stress intensity factors. The conventional stress intensity factors K_I, K_{II}, K_{IV} for a notch in a homogeneous piezoelectric material and the in-plane problem are then defined as

$$\mathbf{k} = \begin{Bmatrix} K_{II} \\ K_I \\ K_{IV} \end{Bmatrix} = \lim_{r \rightarrow 0} \sqrt{2\pi} \langle r^{1-\text{Re}(\delta_i)} \rangle \tilde{\Lambda}_{,x_1} \left\langle \left(\frac{r}{l}\right)^{-i\text{Im}(\delta_i)} \right\rangle \tilde{\Lambda}_{,x_1}^{-1} \begin{Bmatrix} \sigma_{21} \\ \sigma_{22} \\ D_2 \end{Bmatrix}_{\theta=0}, \quad (50)$$

or, using Eq.(49)

$$\mathbf{k} = \begin{Bmatrix} K_{II} \\ K_I \\ K_{IV} \end{Bmatrix} = \sqrt{2\pi} \tilde{\Lambda}_{,x_1} \begin{Bmatrix} \tilde{H}_1 \\ \tilde{H}_2 \\ \tilde{H}_3 \end{Bmatrix}. \quad (51)$$

In case of interface crack between two dissimilar piezoelectric materials it is advantageous to compare the energy release rate values, G , to assess the overall influence of the domain switching zone. First, it is convenient to introduce the matrix \mathbf{M} as

$$\mathbf{M} = -i\mathbf{L}\mathbf{A}^{-1} \quad (52)$$

where $i = \sqrt{-1}$ and matrices \mathbf{A} and \mathbf{L} are defined in Appendix. The real and imaginary parts of the bimaterial matrix $\mathbf{M}^* = (\mathbf{M}^I)^{-1} + (\mathbf{M}^{II})^{-1} = \mathbf{B}_0^I + \overline{\mathbf{B}_0^{II}} = \mathbf{D} - i\mathbf{W}$, see Eqs. (16), (17), can be conveniently expressed as

$$\mathbf{D} = \text{Re}(\mathbf{M}^*), \quad \mathbf{W} = \text{Im}(\mathbf{M}^*) \quad (53)$$

G can be expressed in terms of stress/electric intensity factor \mathbf{k} as (Hwu & Ikeda, 2008)

$$G = \frac{1}{4} \mathbf{k}^T \{ \mathbf{D} + \mathbf{W}\mathbf{D}^{-1}\mathbf{W} \} \mathbf{k}. \quad (54)$$

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In this paper, only mechanical loading is considered and the local GSIFs $H_i^{tip} = H_i + \Delta H_i$, which include effects of the switching zone, are calculated only for the special case of an interface crack. The geometry and boundary conditions are stated in Fig. 2. The switching criterion (28) was considered in the vicinity of the notch tip. The changes in the spontaneous strain and the spontaneous polarization during switching are considered as given in Eqs. (29), (30) and the magnitudes of the spontaneous polarization, spontaneous strain, and the coercive electric field are given in Tab. 1. Elastic, piezoelectric, and electric material characteristics of piezoelectric ceramics PZT-5H and BaTiO₃ forming the bimaterial sample are also presented in Tab. 1. The initial poling directions in both materials are considered to be parallel because, as we have shown in (Hrstka et al., 2019), parallel poling directions maximize the singularity of the stress and

electric displacement field independently on the orientation of the poling directions with respect to the interface, thus representing the most critical case from the point of fracture inception. The GSIFs H_i (the effects of the switching zone are not included) for the considered notch configurations and for the stated material combination are given in Tab. 2. The conventional stress intensity factors K_I , K_{II} , K_{IV} calculated from Eq.(51) are also given. The reference length was chosen as $l = 1$ mm. If the exponent δ_i is real-valued, so is the corresponding GSIF. Two distinct complex GSIFs are obtained for complex conjugate exponents δ_i . The third exponent is always real, just as its stress intensity factor. The applied loading was chosen as $\sigma_2^{\text{appl}} = 5$ MPa which ensures the small-scale domain switching with respect to the dimensions of piezoelectric bi-material sample shown in Fig. 2 and allows to use asymptotic fields in the criterion (28).

Fig. 2. Considered geometries and boundary conditions of a piezoelectric bi-material sample with (a) an interface crack, (b) a bi-material notch with the angle $\omega_1 = 150^\circ$, the second face remains $\omega_2 = 180^\circ$, $a = 180$ mm, $b = 180$ mm.

The full-field solution enabling to extract both H_i and H_i^{tip} stress intensity factors was determined by using finite element method implemented in the FEniCS Project, version 2019.1.0. The numerical integration of the contour integrals in Eqs. (26) and (45) was performed by the Romberg's integration method. Details of the calculations of the contour integrals are given in our previous paper (Hrstka et al., 2019). The complete computational procedure is illustrated in Fig. 3. Firstly, an interface crack problem between two dissimilar piezoelectric materials is considered. Then, the singularity exponents and stress intensity factors are computed by using Eqs. (18), (25) and (51). The full-field solution is obtained from the FEM model with geometry, boundary conditions and loading specified in Fig. 2. In the material interface, ideal adhesion is assumed. Triangular quadratic plane elements are considered under plane strain condition. The piezoelectric behaviour is realized by coupled mixed-form finite element formulation. The domain switching zones are then determined by application of the criterion (28). After that, the zone contours are extracted and included in the above-mentioned FEM model, see Fig. 3. The initial conditions $\Delta \varepsilon_{ij}$ and ΔP_i , with respect to the nature of the switching, are inserted into the constitutive law (33) describing the mechanical behaviour of the zones. In addition, the poling direction is rotated according to the switching angle, i.e., 90° or -90° , respectively (red or blue colour in Fig. 3, respectively). That means the material constant in the matrices $\hat{\mathbf{C}}'_E$, $\hat{\mathbf{e}}'$ and $\hat{\mathbf{w}}'_\varepsilon$ are rotated according to the switching angle. The boundary conditions and external geometry of the model remain unchanged. Finally, the tip stress intensity factors are extracted by using Eq. (45). Computation of the surface integral over the switching domains in Eq. (45) was performed by using 7-point Gauss quadrature over the triangle extracted from the mesh. The Gaussian points and weights are stated in (Dunavant D. A., 1985) in its Appendix II for $p = 5$. The finite element mesh in the domain switching zones was very fine, the edge length was 3-4 μm in order to cover the analytical functions in the utmost vicinity to the crack tip.

It is interesting to note that all singularity exponents for the bi-material notch with the angle $\omega_1 = 150^\circ$ are real. The switching zone predicted from the criterion (28) by employing the linear asymptotic field in Eq. (12) with evaluated GSIFs H_i is shown for two selected notch geometries in Figs. 4-5.

Tab. 1. Materials properties of transversally isotropic piezoelectric ceramics PZT-5H and BaTiO₃ poled in x_1 -direction

Material constant	PZT-5H (Material 1)	BaTiO ₃ (Material 2)
$C_{11}^E \times 10^{10}$ [Pa]	11.7	14.6
$C_{12}^E \times 10^{10}$ [Pa]	5.3	6.6
$C_{23}^E \times 10^{10}$ [Pa]	5.5	6.6
$C_{22}^E \times 10^{10}$ [Pa]	12.60	15.0
$C_{44}^E \times 10^{10}$ [Pa]	3.53	4.4
e_{11} [Cm ⁻²]	23.3	17.5
e_{12} [Cm ⁻²]	-6.50	-4.35
e_{26} [Cm ⁻²]	17.0	11.4
$\omega_{11}^\epsilon \times 10^{-9}$ [C(Vm) ⁻¹]	13.0	11.2
$\omega_{22}^\epsilon \times 10^{-9}$ [C(Vm) ⁻¹]	15.1	9.87
E_c [kVm ⁻¹]	800	350
P_s [N(Vm) ⁻¹]	0.39	0.3
γ_s [-]	0.004	0.005

TABLE 2. Generalized stress intensity factors for two considered PZT-5H/ BaTiO₃ piezoelectric bi-material notches with poling direction $\alpha_1 = \alpha_2 = 90^\circ$ and loaded by $\sigma_2^{\text{appl}} = 5$ MPa

ω_1 [°]	δ_1	H_1 [MPa · mm ^{1-δ_1}]	K_{II} [MPa · $\sqrt{\text{m}}$]
	δ_2	H_2 [MPa · mm ^{1-δ_2}]	K_I [MPa · $\sqrt{\text{m}}$]
	δ_3	H_3 [MPa · mm ^{1-δ_3}]	K_{IV} [mC · $\sqrt{\text{m}}$]
150	0.5079	92.5909	-0.6966
	0.5359	-3.3950	8.2349
	0.6036	2.5567	0.8592
180	0.5+0.0129i	91.7693-9.2309i	-0.7112
	0.5-0.0129i	84.6092+8.5107i	7.6952
	0.5	-32.4600	0.9941

Observe that the switching zone predominantly develops in Material 2 because the criterion (28) is met easier in Material 2 due to significantly lower value of the coercive electric field, see Tab. 1. The orientation of the switching angle i.e. 90° or -90° , depends on the criterion (28), priority is given to the orientation for which the criterion (28) is met first. The orientation of the initial poling direction given by the angle α has a marking influence on the size of the switching zone and on its two lobes structure in Material 2. In case of the interface crack it can be seen that for $\alpha < 30^\circ$ the model predicts that the switching zone develops only in Material 2 while already for $\alpha \approx 10^\circ$ the smaller lobe adjoining to the crack face exhibits switching

Fig. 3. Scheme of the computation procedure

Fig 4. Domain switching zones for an interface crack loaded by $\sigma_2^{appl} = 5$ MPa for various orientations of the initial poling direction with respect to the interface; on the left-hand side the detailed view is shown

Fig 5. Domain switching zones for a bi-material notch with the angle $\omega_1 = 150$ loaded by $\sigma_2^{\text{appl}} = 5$ MPa for various orientations of the initial poling direction with respect to the interface; on the left-hand side the detailed view is shown

about 90° and the major lobe exhibits switching about -90° . With increasing α the size of the switching zone decreases reaching minimum for $\alpha \approx 60^\circ$. It is interesting to note that the lobe with switching about -90° in Material 2 completely disappears for $\alpha \approx 80^\circ$. Then the size of the switching zone increases again reaching maximum for $\alpha = 180^\circ$ and the lobe with switching about 90° disappears. It can be observed in Fig. 5 that domain switching zone for a bi-material notch with the angle $\omega_1 = 150^\circ$ develops for various orientations of the initial poling direction in a similar fashion as in the case of the interface crack.

Figs. 6-10 show asymptotic displacements, stress components, electric displacement components and electric potential along the circular path with radius $r = 1$ mm around the interface crack tip for orientations of the initial poling direction $\alpha = 0^\circ, 70^\circ, 90^\circ, 120^\circ, 180^\circ$. The switching zone markedly influences resulting asymptotic fields as it can be seen when the local GSIFs $H_i^{tip} = H_i + \Delta H_i$ are used to evaluate the asymptotic fields. The results in Figs. 6-10 show that, except of the orientations of the initial poling direction close to limit values $\alpha = 0^\circ, 180^\circ$, the presence of switching zone for considered material properties of bimaterial sample reduces mechanical asymptotic fields but amplifies electrical asymptotic fields. Remarkable is there an increase of potential difference between crack surfaces, especially for $\alpha \in 90^\circ - 130^\circ$ accompanied by a large increase of the electric displacement component D_2 ahead of the crack tip. Another point is also interesting - whilst before switching is the stress σ_{11} discontinuous across the interface, after switching it gets closer for $\alpha \in 90^\circ - 130^\circ$ and the jump is not very significant (the stress is almost continuous).

Fig 6. The displacements, stress components, electric displacement components and electric potential along the circular path $r = 1$ mm for a PZT-5H/BaTiO₃ interface crack, $\alpha = 0^\circ$, loading $\sigma_2^{\text{appl}} = 5$ MPa

Fig. 7. The displacements, stress components, electric displacement components and electric potential along the circular path $r = 1$ mm for a PZT-5H/BaTiO₃ interface crack, $\alpha = 70^\circ$, loading $\sigma_2^{\text{appl}} = 5$ MPa

Fig. 8. The displacements, stress components, electric displacement components and electric potential along the circular path $r = 1$ mm for a PZT-5H/BaTiO₃ interface crack, $\alpha = 90^\circ$, loading $\sigma_2^{\text{appl}} = 5$ MPa

Fig. 9. The displacements, stress components, electric displacement components and electric potential along the circular path $r = 1$ mm for a PZT-5H/BaTiO₃ interface crack, $\alpha = 120^\circ$, loading $\sigma_2^{\text{appl}} = 5$ MPa

Fig. 10. The displacements, stress components, electric displacement components and electric potential along the circular path $r = 1$ mm for a PZT-5H/BaTiO₃ interface crack, $\alpha = 180^\circ$, loading $\sigma_2^{\text{app1}} = 5$ MPa

Fig. 11 shows the conventional stress intensity factors calculated using Eq. (50) as functions of the initial poling direction before switching K_{II} , K_I , K_{IV} , and after switching K_{II}^{tip} , K_I^{tip} , K_{IV}^{tip} . It is seen that while before switching the stress intensity factors depend only weakly on the initial poling direction, after switching they strongly vary with the initial poling direction. Mechanical SIFs K_{II}^{tip} , K_I^{tip} are significantly reduced for the initial poling direction values $\alpha \in (40^\circ, 120^\circ - 140^\circ)$, while the electrical SIF K_{IV}^{tip} is significantly amplified within this interval of α , which is in accord with the asymptotic fields shown in Figs. 6-10. The ratios $K_{II}^{\text{tip}}/K_{II}$, K_I^{tip}/K_I , $K_{IV}^{\text{tip}}/K_{IV}$ are plotted in Fig. 12, which better represent the influence of switching

Fig. 11. Stress intensity factors as functions of the orientation of the initial poling direction calculated from Eq. (50)

Fig. 12. Ratios $K_{II}^{tip}/K_{II}, K_I^{tip}/K_I, K_{IV}^{tip}/K_{IV}$ plotted as functions of the initial poling direction

domain independently on the applied load under assumption of small scale switching. It is known, see e.g. (Hwu & Ikeda, 2008), that in case of interface crack the mechanical load alone can induce nonzero value of the electrical intensity factor K_{IV} for in-plane poling. The presented results show that this effect can be distinctly intensified due to poling switching.

As already mentioned in the previous section, it is more convenient to compare the energy release rate values to assess the overall influence of the domain switching zone in case of interface crack between two dissimilar piezoelectric materials. The energy release rate before switching, G , and after switching, G^{tip} , was calculated using Eq. (54) as function of the orientation of the initial poling direction. The total energy release rate, the mechanical energy release rate (labelled in Fig.12 as “without K_{IV}^2 ”) and the pure electrical energy release rate were plotted both before and after switching. It is well known that linear piezoelectricity always predicts that the electrical contribution to the energy release rate is negative. Here, the pure electrical energy release rate before switching is negligible in comparison to mechanical one, as it can be seen in Fig. 13, because only mechanical load of the interface crack is considered and the induced electrical intensity factor K_{IV} is low, see red line in Fig.11c. Nevertheless, the switching model predicts that the electrical contribution to the energy release rate after switching becomes dominant and makes the total energy release rate negative for the initial poling direction values $\alpha \in (40^\circ, 150^\circ)$, see Fig. 13. Fig. 14 then shows the ratios G^{tip}/G of the total energy release rate and the mechanical energy release rate only plotted as functions of the initial poling direction. The strong negative electrical contribution to the energy release rate due to switching can be explained using the crack closure integral expression

$$G = \lim_{\Delta a \rightarrow 0} \frac{1}{2a} \int_0^{\Delta a} [\Delta u_1(\Delta a - s)\sigma_{12}(s) + \Delta u_2(\Delta a - s)\sigma_{22}(s) + D_2(s)\Delta\phi(\Delta a - s)]ds \quad (55)$$

with $\Delta u_i, \Delta\phi$ standing for the jumps of displacements and of the electric potential over the crack faces, and results shown in Figs. 7-9. In these figures one can observe that poling switching induces a remarkable negative increase of potential difference over the crack faces accompanied by a large increase of the electric

displacement component D_2 ahead of the crack tip. As a result, the last term in the integrand of the crack closure integral obtains large negative values for the initial poling direction values $\alpha \in (40^\circ, 150^\circ)$.

Fig. 13. Energy release rate before switching, G , and after switching, G^{tip} , as function of the orientation of the initial poling direction calculated from Eq. (54)

Fig. 14. Ratios G^{tip}/G plotted as functions of the initial poling direction

CONCLUSIONS

For the first time a theoretical model was proposed to analyse small-scale domain switching near an interface crack in PZT-5H/BaTiO₃ bi-material and its impact upon the energy release rate under pure mechanical loading. The simple energy-based criterion proposed in (Hwang et al., 1995) was applied for prediction of the domain switching zone ahead of the interface crack and the bi-material notch with the angle $\omega_1 = 150$. As boundary conditions only traction and charge free faces were considered. It was shown that the orientation of the initial poling has a marking influence on the size and the shape of the switching zone. The effects of the switching zone upon the local electromechanical field was calculated only for the special case of an interface crack under pure mechanical loading. Consequently, the energy release rates before switching, G , and after switching, G^{tip} , were calculated as functions of the orientation of the initial poling direction. A remarkable influence of the initial poling direction was found making the total energy release rate negative for the initial poling direction values $\alpha \in \langle 40^\circ, 150^\circ \rangle$ due to dominant electrical contribution to the energy release rate after switching.

To conclude, a robust computational procedure based upon the expanded Lekhnitskii-Eshelby-Stroh formalism was developed to evaluate the influence of domain switching zone on the in-plane asymptotic field of the bi-material sharp notch and the interface crack in a generally monoclinic piezoelectric bi-material. Betti's reciprocal principle was applied to calculate the general stress intensity factors and also to capture the influence the domain switching zone, thus avoiding a derivation of weight functions. As a next step, formulation of fracture criteria and experimental verification would be desirable. Also application of the semi-permeable crack boundary conditions and so-called energetically consistent boundary conditions is required to analyse the role of electric crack face boundary conditions on domain switching in case of interface cracks and bi-material notches.

APPENDIX A

The complex function \mathbf{Z}^{δ_i} in Eq. (13) is defined as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{Z}^{\delta_i}(\theta) &= \text{diag}[R_1^{\delta_i}(\theta)e^{i\delta_i\psi_1(\theta)}, R_2^{\delta_i}(\theta)e^{i\delta_i\psi_2(\theta)}, R_3^{\delta_i}(\theta)e^{i\delta_i\psi_3(\theta)}], \\ \bar{\mathbf{Z}}^{\delta_i}(\theta) &= \text{diag}[R_1^{\delta_i}(\theta)e^{-i\delta_i\psi_1(\theta)}, R_2^{\delta_i}(\theta)e^{-i\delta_i\psi_2(\theta)}, R_3^{\delta_i}(\theta)e^{-i\delta_i\psi_3(\theta)}], \end{aligned} \quad (\text{A1})$$

where

$$R_k^2(\theta) = (\cos \theta + \mu'_k \sin \theta)^2 + (\mu''_k \sin \theta)^2, \quad (k = 1, 2, 3), \quad (\text{A2})$$

$$\psi_k(\theta) = \begin{cases} \arctan\left(\frac{\mu''_k \sin \theta}{\cos \theta + \mu'_k \sin \theta}\right) & \text{for } \theta > -\pi, \\ -\pi & \text{for } \theta = -\pi \end{cases}, \quad (k = 1, 2, 3). \quad (\text{A3})$$

The symbols μ'_k, μ''_k denote real and imaginary part of the material eigenvalue μ_k , which is the root of the following characteristic equation

$$l_2(\mu)[l_4(\mu)\rho_2(\mu) - m_3^2(\mu)] = 0, \quad (\text{A4})$$

$$\begin{aligned} l_2(\mu) &= \hat{S}_{55}^D \mu^2 - 2\hat{S}_{45}^D \mu + \hat{S}_{44}^D, \\ l_4(\mu) &= \hat{S}_{11}^D \mu^4 - 2\hat{S}_{16}^D \mu^3 + (2\hat{S}_{12}^D + \hat{S}_{66}^D) \mu^2 - 2\hat{S}_{26}^D \mu + \hat{S}_{22}^D, \\ m_3(\mu) &= \hat{g}'_{11} \mu^3 - (\hat{g}'_{21} + \hat{g}'_{16}) \mu^2 + (\hat{g}'_{12} + \hat{g}'_{26}) \mu - \hat{g}'_{22}, \\ \rho_2(\mu) &= -\hat{\beta}'_{11} \mu^2 + 2\hat{\beta}'_{12} \mu - \hat{\beta}'_{22}. \end{aligned} \quad (\text{A5})$$

and matrices \mathbf{A} and \mathbf{L} in Eq. (13) are

$$\mathbf{A} = \begin{bmatrix} a_{11} & a_{12} & a_{14} \\ a_{21} & a_{22} & a_{24} \\ a_{41} & a_{42} & a_{44} \end{bmatrix}, \quad \mathbf{L} = \begin{bmatrix} -\mu_1 & -\mu_2 & -\mu_4 \xi_4 \\ 1 & 1 & \xi_4 \\ -\xi_1 & -\xi_2 & -1 \end{bmatrix}, \quad (\text{A6})$$

where

$$\begin{aligned} a_{1k} &= \mu_k^2 \hat{S}'_{11} + \hat{S}'_{12} - \mu_k \hat{S}'_{16} + \xi_k (\mu_k \hat{g}'_{11} - \hat{g}'_{21}), \quad (k = 1, 2) \\ a_{2k} &= [\mu_k^2 \hat{S}'_{12} + \hat{S}'_{22} - \mu_k \hat{S}'_{26} + \xi_k (\mu_k \hat{g}'_{12} - \hat{g}'_{22})] / \mu_k, \quad (k = 1, 2), \\ a_{4k} &= [\mu_k^2 \hat{g}'_{21} + \hat{g}'_{22} - \mu_k \hat{g}'_{26} + \xi_k (-\mu_k \hat{\beta}'_{12} + \hat{\beta}'_{22})] / \mu_k, \quad (k = 1, 2) \\ a_{14} &= (\mu_4^2 \hat{S}'_{11} + \hat{S}'_{12} - \mu_4 \hat{S}'_{16}) \xi_4 + \mu_4 \hat{g}'_{11} - \hat{g}'_{21}, \\ a_{24} &= [(\mu_4^2 \hat{S}'_{12} + \hat{S}'_{22} - \mu_4 \hat{S}'_{26}) \xi_4 + \mu_4 \hat{g}'_{12} - \hat{g}'_{22}] / \mu_4, \\ a_{44} &= [(\mu_4^2 \hat{g}'_{21} + \hat{g}'_{22} - \mu_4 \hat{g}'_{26}) \xi_4 - \mu_4 \hat{\beta}'_{12} + \hat{\beta}'_{22}] / \mu_4, \end{aligned} \quad (\text{A7})$$

and

$$\xi_k = -\frac{l_2(\mu_k) m_3(\mu_k)}{\rho_2(\mu_k) l_2(\mu_k)}, \quad (k = 1, 2), \quad (\text{A8})$$

$$\xi_k = -\frac{l_2(\mu_k) m_3(\mu_k)}{l_2(\mu_k) l_4(\mu_k)}. \quad (k = 4). \quad (\text{A9})$$

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